

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Health Care Workers Towards the Care of the Elderly in PHCC Mubi South Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Aging is a universal phenomenon that is obvious as well as inevitable. Old age is a significant stage in life and normally related to life expectancy of given area, hence the conditions and the needs of the aged becomes imperative. Care of the elderly is the fulfillment of the special needs and requirements that are unique to senior citizens. It covers such services as assisted living, adult day care, long term care, nursing homes, hospice care and home care. This study was aimed to assessed knowledge, attitude and practice of health care workers towards the care of the elderly in PHCC Mubi South Local Government Area of Adamawa State. A cross-sectional research design was employed with 108 sampled calculated using Yamane's formula. Proportionate allocation and simple random sampling

technique was adopted to select the HCW from each PHCC. The structured interviewer questionnaire was used to collect data. An ethical approval was obtained and permission granted for the study. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 22.0 where the results has been and presented in tables and diagrams. The study revealed that there is good knowledge (82%), attitude (65%) and practice (64%) of the care of the elderly. Healthcare workers' knowledge, attitude and practice play a major role in the care of the elderly at PHCC and concerns authorities should continue to support the care of the elderly.

Keywords: *Knowledge, attitude, practice, care of the elderly, Mubi*

Introduction

Ageing is one of the characteristics of humans which involve the accumulation of changes in a person over time. It involves a multidimensional

process of physical, psychological and social change. Some dimensions of aging grow and expand over time, while others decline. Ageing is not a disease; but phase of life where there is

retrograde biological process in growth and development which leads to decreased powers for survival and adjustment. Aging is an important part of all human societies reflecting the biological changes that occur and also reflecting cultural and societal convention (Hoyer & Roodin, 2013).

The World Health Organization (WHO) has always designated as “Elderly” people aged 65 years and above. Older people make up an increasing proportion of the population in developed world and this demographic transition also affects some developing countries. Generally older people are at increased risk of disease, disability, social and financial deprivation compared to the younger generation in the same population. An increase in the number of older people may lead to increased demands on health and support services including aged care residential services and acute health service (NCPOP, 2017).

There are 703 million persons aged 65 years or over in the world in 2019. The number of older persons is projected to double to 1.5 billion in 2050. Globally, the share of the population aged 65 years or over increased from 6% in 1990 to 9% in 2019. That proportion is projected to rise further to 16% by 2050, so that one in six people in the world will be aged 65 years or over (World Population Prospects, 2019).

In 2022, population aged 65 years and above for Nigeria was 3%. Population aged 65 years and above of Nigeria fell gradually from 3.3% in 1973 to 3% in 2022 (Knoema World Data Atlas and Statistics of Nigeria, 2023).

Care of the elderly is the fulfillment of the special needs and requirements that are unique to senior citizens. It covers such services as assisted living, adult day care, long term care, nursing homes, hospice care and home care. Elderly care emphasizes the social and personal requirements of senior citizens who need some assistance with daily activities and health care, but who desire to age with dignity. The care of the elderly is multidimensional and these include physical, emotional, spiritual and social care. Providing care especially to the elderly, takes a huge toll, both physically and emotionally on the caregiver.

With the population of the elderly growing in Nigeria, one of the emerging issues is the care and support of elderly persons in years to come. Few people are prepared for the responsibilities and tasks of caring for the elderly because of the stress involved (Okoye, & Asa, 2011).

Health care workers are very important workers with obligation of health (Okafor, 2009). A cursory look at the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the federal government shows that there is little or no consideration of this very important segment of the population – the elderly (Donatelle, 2018). Those involved in the provision of health care have important roles to play in the programmed relating to elderly care especially in screening and detecting abuse. Care of the elderly requires adequate knowledge of the ageing process, nutrition and daily needs of the elderly (Oyetunde et al., 2013).

It is important for health workers to have adequate knowledge on the basic needs of the elderly than the rest of the population.⁵ This is necessary because these needs must be met every day for the elderly to be able to live independently for as long as possible and Caretakers would be able to help the aged meet these needs without compromising their health and safety. These needs include personal Hygiene, mobility, nutrition, doctors’ visit and prescription and physical activity (exercise) (Okoye, & Asa, 2011).

Ageism is the systematic, stereotyping of discrimination against people because they are old. This is perpetuated by the portrayal of older people as frail, ill, suffering mental deterioration, poor and dependent, and the alternative portrayal of living affluent life styles and scrounging off the welfare state (O’Neill, & O’Keeffe, 2003).

Health workers are at risk of developing ageist attitudes because they are exposed to a disproportionate percentage of ill or dependent older people (Doherty, Mitchell, & O’Neill, 2011). Attribution of ill health to ageing, low economic status and negative attitude of health workers towards the care of the elderly are some of the factors associated with delay in seeking

health care (Doherty, Mitchell, & O'Neill, 2011). Research has also shown that the quality of health care service provided to older population is strongly influenced by care givers attitude towards older people (Kaur et al., 2014).

Effective care of the elderly requires special training, provision of geriatric ward, adequate staffing to reduce stress and improved quality care (Oyetunde et al., 2013). The factors that positively influenced health workers attitude to the care of the elderly were years of experience, age and mental state of the elderly. There was significant association ($P < 0.05$) between attitude of Health Workers and mean years of experience. Workers with less years of experience had negative attitude, while those with more years of experience had positive attitude, towards the care of the elderly (Efiong, 2015).

The population of the elderly in the world is increasing rapidly and the rate of increase is higher in developing societies including Mubi Metropolis. The researcher has observed that most health workers have very poor knowledge of mental health conditions which are common with the elderly and as such health workers come to service with deep seated, negative, diluted and superstitious belief about caring for the elderly. This lack of adequate knowledge and negative attitude towards the care of the elderly may result in serious problems in our society in the near future. Attitude is a state of readiness organized through experiences upon individuals' response to all objects and situations. Attitudes are generally positive or negative perception of a person about a place, thing or event (Zeng et al., 2019).

In this study, HCWS are individuals or group of people such as community health officers, community health extension workers, and junior community health officers who are well trained in the field of health to render adequate health care services to ensure optimum well-being of the young, the ageing and the elderly (Abudu-Birresborn et al., 2019). Therefore, attitude of healthcare professional in the context of this study is perceived as a set of effective reactions, opinions and feelings that healthcare

professionals hold towards the elderly attending the health care centers in Mubi South LGA, Adamawa State. The ageing process is a period of physical and psychological declining. It can only be delayed but it must surely come with its sign and symptoms (Abudu-Birresborn et al., 2019).

In this study, ageism is referred to as a natural process which involves biological, mental, social and physiological growth and development, followed by declines which occur in people as they live towards death. The aged patients in the context of this study are perceived as all those who have attained and advanced age of 65 and above who seek health care at selected health centers in Mubi South LGA, Adamawa state. However, there is dearth of literature on attitude of HCWs towards the care of the elderly patient attending health care centers in Mubi South LGA, Adamawa State.

Methodology

Study Area

Mubi South Local Government Area is situated in Adamawa State North-east geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Mubi South LGA shares boundaries with Maiha LGA in the south, Cameroon to the east, Mubi North LGA to the north and Hong LGA to the west, The LGA is part of the Mubi Emirate and is made up of several towns and villages. The area hosts members of diverse ethnic affiliations with the most populous in the LGA being the Gude, Nzanyi, Fali, Fulani and Hausa; Mubi south has a total population of 129,956 and projection of 200,400 in 2022 of which majority of them are Christians and Muslims, they depends on farming and business as their major source of incomes. They receive health care services at PHC Mubi south, PHC Mubi north and General Hospital Mubi south respectively.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study design was used.

Study Population

The study population consists of healthcare workers that provide direct and indirect services to the elderly patients were included and those that were not around because they are either on annual leave or duty shift off during the study were excluded.

Sample Size determination

The sample size was calculated using Yamane's formula for minimum sample size determination which was 108 health care workers participated in the study.

Sampling Procedure

After proportionate allocation, the respondent that satisfied the eligibility criteria were selected by simple random sampling by balloting from the selected health facilities Lamorde PHCC, Nassarawo PHCC, Gella PHCC, Mugulbu PHCC and Nduku PHCC after obtaining a sampling frame and sampling interval until the minimum sample size was exhausted.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was an interviewer questionnaire that consists of five (5) sections. Section A Socio-demographic profile of the respondents, Section B knowledge of health workers towards care of the elderly, Section C attitude of health workers towards care of the elderly, Section D health care workers practice towards care for the elderly, Section E factors influencing the attitude of health workers on care of the elderly. The questionnaire subjected to panels for face and content validity, their modifications and suggestion were effected before final approval for this study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered the questionnaires to the sampled health workers at their work place when they were less busy in the facility to avoid interfering with their routine services.

Data Analysis

The data entered into excel spread sheet and clean, then it was analyzed using SPSS version 22.0 and the results were presented in frequency tables and diagrams.

Ethical Consideration

An ethical clearance was obtained and permission was granted by Mubi South LGA to conduct the study after obtaining a written informed consent from all the participants.

Results

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Where age ranged from 20-29 made 30% followed by 30-39 with 27%, 40-49 24% and lastly >50 with 19%. With regards to sex of the respondents, female were 63% while male made up 37%. The majority of the respondents were Gude by tribe with 45%. On the educational status, 86% have tertiary education and 36% of the respondents were working within 1-5 years, 26% within 6-10 years, 19% within 11-20 years and 19% for greater than 21 years.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristic

	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Age		
20-29	32	30%
30-39	29	27%
40-49	27	24%
>50	20	19%
Total	108	100
Sex		
Female	68	63%
Male	40	37%
Total	108	100
Tribe		
Gude	49	45%
Fulani	10	9%
Hausa	17	16%
Higgi	16	15%
Nzayi	16	15%
Total	108	100
Marital Status		
Divorce	8	7%
Married	58	55%
Single	35	32%
Widow	7	6%
Total	108	100
Educational status		
Non formal	4	4%
Primary	3	3%
Secondary	8	7%

Tertiary	93	86%
Total	108	100
Religion		
Christian	60	56%
Islam	48	44%
Total	108	100
Professional qualification		
Chew/CHO	33	31%
Nurses/Midwife	8	8%
Jchew	27	25%
Others (Pharm. Tech, Lab...)	40	37%
Total	108	100
Years of working experience		
1-5years	39	36%
6-10years	28	26%
11-20years	21	19%
>21years	20	19%
Total	108	100

Level of knowledge of Health Care Workers towards Care of the Elderly

Figure 1. Pie Chart Illustrating Respondents' Level of Knowledge Towards Care of the Elderly

The diagrams above revealed majority of the respondents 82% and 18% have good and poor knowledge towards care of the elderly.

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents 72% knows an elderly is a person ages 65 years and above while 28% said no then 84% knows that aging process leads to anatomical and physiological changes whereas 16% don't know.

Respondents have different view on types of supportive cares needed by an elderly as 77% responded that nutritional support should be provided, 23% said no and 89%, 84% and 80%, advocate for medical, social and emotional support respectively. About the common conditions associated with an elderly people 93%, 85% and 60% indicates hearing impairment, hypertension and senile dementia respectively.

Table 2. Knowledge of Health Care Workers towards the Care of the Elderly

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Elderly is a person ages 65 years and above		
No	23	28%
Yes	78	72%
Total	108	100
Ageing process leads to anatomical and physiological changes		
No	17	16%
Yes	91	84%
Total	108	100
Supportive cares needed by an elderly		
Nutritional support		
No	25	23%
Yes	83	77%
Total	108	100
Medical Support		
No	12	11%
Yes	96	89%
Total	108	100
Emotional Support		
No	23	20%
Yes	85	80%
Total	108	100
Social Supports		
No	17	16%
Yes	91	84%
Total	108	100
Common conditions associated with an elderly people		
No	11	10%
Yes	97	90%
Total	108	100
Hearing Impairments		
No	8	7%
Yes	100	93%
Total	108	100
Senile Dementia		
No	43	40%
Yes	65	60%
Total	108	100
Hypertension		

No	16	15%
Yes	92	85%
Total	108	100

The diagram (figure 2) shows that majority 65% and 35% of the respondents have positive and negative attitude towards care of the elderly.

Figure 2. Pie Chart Illustrating Attitude of Healthcare Workers Towards Care of the Elderly

Table 3 shows the respondents view on weather displaying positive attitudes toward care of an elderly improves efficiency of the services 90% said yes and 92% pointed discrimination of an elder person as negative attitude toward their care. It worthy to note that 72% of the respondents said healthcare workers are not at risk of becoming ageist and 28% responded yes Meanwhile, 52% of the respondents believed that lack of formal geriatric care education affects the attitude of health care workers.

Table 3. Attitude of Health Workers Towards Care of the Elderly

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Displaying positive attitudes toward care of an elderly improves efficiency of the services		
No	11	10%
Yes	97	90%
Total	108	100%

Discrimination of an elder person a negative attitude toward their care		
No	9	8%
Yes	99	92%
Total	108	100%
Health workers are at risk of developing ageist attitude		
No	78	72%
Yes	30	28%
Total	108	100%
Lack of formal geriatric care education affect the attitude of the health worker		
No	52	48%
Yes	56	52%
Total	108	100%

The table 4 shows that 64% of the respondents were offering elderly care services then 40% were offering the services daily, 16% weekly, 9% monthly and 36% have not indicate their opinions. While 19%, 22% and 7% said inadequate staff, lack of skills and no facility to offer the services.

Table 4. Practice of Health Care Workers Towards Care of the Elderly

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Offering elderly care services in your facility		
No	39	36%
Yes	69	64%
Total	108	100%
Frequency services offered		
No response	39	36%
Daily	43	40%
Monthly	9	8%
Weekly	17	16%
Total	108	100%
Reason for not offering the services		
Inadequate staff		
No response	70	65%
No	17	16%
Yes	21	19%
Total	108	100%
Lack of skills on care of the elderly		
No response	71	66%
No	13	12%
Yes	24	22%
Total	108	100%
Others (specify)		
No response	80	74%
Lack equipment	21	19%
No facility	7	7%
Total	108	100%

The table 5 shows that 65% of the respondents believed that socio-demographic factor affects the attitude of health workers toward care of an elderly. The table also contains information on the factors influencing the respondents toward care of the elderly in which majority 92% of them believed is to improve their wellbeing, quality of life and to identify and manage conditions affecting them. However, 10%, 15%, 7%, 8%, 10% and 35% of the respondents added prevention of depression, improving quality of life, preventing loneliness, preventing accidents and prevent diseases as factors influencing them toward care of the elderly people.

Table 5. Factors Influencing the Attitude of Health Workers on Care of the Elderly

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Socio-demographic factors affect the attitude of health worker toward care of an elderly		
No	38	35%
Yes	70	65%
Total	108	100%
What influence you to provide care for the elderly		
a. To improve their wellbeing		
No response	2	2%
No	3	3%
Yes	103	95%
Total	108	100%
b. To promote their lives		
No	12	11%
Yes	96	89%
Total	108	100%
c. To identify and manage their conditions		
No	10	9.3%
Yes	98	90.7%
Total	108	100%
d. Others		
No response	16	15%
Improve quality of life	11	10%
Prevent depression	15	14%
Prevent disease	38	35%
Prevent loneliness	7	7%
Prolong life	9	8%
To have sense of belonging	1	1%
To prevent accidents	11	10%
Total	108	100%

Discussion

The study revealed that majority of the respondents 30% ages between 20-29 with a mean of 2.2 and standard deviation of ± 1.0 . 63% of the respondents were females, and majority 45% were Gude by tribes, majority 55% were married followed by 35 single. 86% of the respondents had attended tertiary institutions; there were 56% Christians and 43% Muslims in the study area. Majority 31% were CHEWs followed by JCHEW's 25%. The result revealed that 36% of the respondents were having less than five years working experience.

The study revealed that majority of the respondents 82% were having good knowledge towards care of the elderly and only 18% were having poor knowledge, this is similar to the study conducted in Calabar in which 96% of the health care workers have good knowledge of the care of elderly However the study contradicts the study conducted in Ethiopia in which only 45% have good knowledge of the care of elderly persons. This may be related to the age, years of working experience and the level of education of the respondents.

The study revealed that majority 65% of the respondents were having positive attitude towards care of the elderly, and only 35% were having negative attitude toward care of the elderly which in line with study conducted in Ibadan on assessment of attitude of health care workers in two selected PHCCs where 81% were having positive attitude and only 19% having negative attitude toward care of the elderly. This may also be related to the age, years of working experience and the level of education of the respondents.

On assessment of the practice of care of elderly, the study revealed that 64% of the respondents were offering elderly care services and only 36% were not offering the services and 40% were offering the services daily, 16% weekly, 9% monthly, it contradicts the study conducted in 22 countries including Belgium, Bagladesh, and Uganda which found that 55% of the respondents reported that Geriatric care practice was not consider a main specialty in their country. It also contradicts the study conducted

in Belgium in which 23% of the study participant reported a poor to a fair level of practice of elderly patients in their unity.

On assessing factors that influence health workers attitude toward care of elderly , the study revealed that 65% of the respondents believed that socio-demographic factors such as age, sex marital status and educations affects the attitude of health workers toward care of the elderly, it very similar to the study conducted by Arani et al, (2017) on assessment of attitudes toward elderly among nurses working in the city of Ilam which revealed that socio demographic factors such as age, gender, education, exposure to well older people, area of practice and professional organizations are factors influencing health care attitudes toward care of elderly. This is related to the good knowledge and attitude of the respondents in this study.

Conclusion

The study revealed health care workers has good, positive and good knowledge, attitude and practice towards care of the elderly at PHCC and concerns authorities should jointly continue to support the care of the elderly.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study health care worker especially the CHEWs being the majority have to further their studies for them to be well updated on the knowledge of care of the elderly.

Government and non-governmental organization should continue supporting the care of the elderly across and all over the level of health care.

Heath care workers should apply the good knowledge and skills they have toward care of the elderly for effective and efficient services.

Government should also provide re creational centers, day care centers and rehabilitation centers for the elderly. Individual, family and community should also intervene in the care of elderly people.

Competing interests

Nil

Authors' contributions

Contributed equally.

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